

Fighting against Climate Change: a non- Traditional Security Threat and Adaptation Challenges in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

For instance, climate change has become an overwhelming concern worldwide. One million deaths occur annually due to problems with climate change, making it the most dangerous nation in Asia, which makes this matter an international concern. This study examines the impact of climate change on immigration, food security, and healthcare. The governmental efforts towards countering climate change in Bangladesh: research Therefore, this report is able to contribute to the campaigns of Bangladesh in international forums against climate change. Climate change affects every country on Earth, and Bangladesh is struggling with it. This is due to the politics involved in the global climate negotiations as well as the extensive investment needed to push onward. Lastly, this study provides several solutions on how they can solve this big hazard in Bangladesh and around the world. Lastly, this study provides several solutions to solve this important risk for Bangladesh as well as the world at large.

INTRODUCTION

The typical weather patterns throughout the world, particularly those related to temperature, precipitation, and severe weather events, are evolving over time. Global warming is a result of human-made activities such as the burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, and heavy industry operations that release greenhouse gases into the atmosphere (Rahman, 2009). Numerous problems that might cause a nation or area to become unstable are included under non-traditional security concerns. These hazards may influence national and international security due to environmental, economic, social, and technological advancements (Anthony, 2008). The challenges that people, communities, and societies have in adapting to the effects of climate change and building resilience are referred to as climate change adaptation problems. Adapting to increasing temperatures, sea level rise, modified precipitation patterns, and more frequent severe weather events are some of these issues. According to Berkhout (2013), adaptation refers to a range of strategies and initiatives used to reduce climate change and guarantee human wellbeing. Bangladesh is suffering greatly from the consequences of climate change, such as rising sea levels, a rise in cyclone frequency, and erratic rainfall patterns. The lives of the low-lying, agricultural, and heavily populated coastal regions are threatened by these issues (Rawlani and Sovacool, 2011; Khatun et al., 2023). Environmental vulnerability refers to a region's or ecosystem's sensitivity to the negative consequences of several stressors, including but not limited to climate change, pollution, deforestation, and resource depletion. Ecological deterioration, biodiversity loss, and increasing human suffering commonly result from populations and ecosystems lacking flexibility and resilience (Ficke, 2007).

"Global warming" refers to the steady rise in the Earth's average surface temperature brought on by the accumulation of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, such as carbon dioxide. Human actions, including the burning of fossil fuels and deforestation, which increase the greenhouse effect and alter climate patterns, sea level rise, and more frequent and intense heatwaves and extreme weather events, are the main causes of this phenomenon (Ussiri and Lal 2017; Islam, 2023). Sea level rise is the progressive increase in the average depth of the seas and coastal waters across the planet. The main causes of this phenomenon are melting glaciers and ice sheets and ocean thermal expansion brought on by global warming. Coastal infrastructure, ecosystems, and populations are in danger from floods, erosive processes, and saltwater intrusion due to sea level rise (Ericson et al. 2006). Dramatic weather events are defined as dramatic deviations from usual weather patterns. There are many instances, including hurricanes, tornadoes, heat waves, cold snaps, droughts, floods, blizzards, wildfires, hailstorms, and heavy rain. They have the potential to cause significant damage and disruption (Fontes, 2021). Changes in well-being, livelihoods, income, and resources are all examples of socioeconomic effects. It explains how some things have an impact on both the social and economic aspects of society (Adger and Kelly, 1999). Security around the globe is increasingly threatened by climate change. Tensions are present around the globe as a result of climate change. Due to the effects of climate change

challenges, the security systems of the majority of governments are now deteriorating. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in the billions of tons, ozone layer destruction that threatens food security, natural catastrophes, and migration that might be a sign of human insecurity are all contributing factors to global warming. Now, a lot of nations and organizations are emphasizing how susceptible they are to climate change. For instance, Bangladesh, a state with low levels of pollution, is experiencing the worst effects of climate change, including strong cyclones, regular flooding, and a danger from rising sea levels to the land. The People's Republic of Bangladesh's administration is working to adapt to climate change; however, doing so is very difficult given that Bangladesh is a poor nation. To lessen this severe issue, collaboration on climate change is required. This essay will support the danger posed by climate change and the difficulties confronting adaptation strategies from that angle.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Climate change is a big security threat issue for the whole world, and many states are in vulnerable situations, like Bangladesh, which is a crystal clear example. Bangladesh has adopted many plans to alleviate and adapt to climate change, and she faces many challenges in solving this issue. This paper will discuss these issues. Previous works were done in that topic which are related to this paper some related works are, according to Islam et al. (2011), he showed the scenario of instability is increasing due to climate change and the security system is declining for the global climate changing pattern with bearing economic damage. Khan et al. (2015), upheld the effects of global warming and the issues faced by Bangladesh and identified some policy recommendations, like funding. According to Haddad et al. (2018), Climate change has posed significant threats to Bangladesh's physical, food, economic, and environmental security. Despite the significant challenges, there are steps that may be taken to mitigate them and given some suggestions to deal with this significant issue in Bangladesh. Ayers et al. (2014), according to this author, argued about adaptation planning with climate change and suggested the idea of climate proofing strategies to mitigate this global concern.

According to Uddin et al. (2017), climate cooperation is necessary to adapt to climate change, and every state must think about one world to mitigate this issue. In accordance with Alston et al. (2016), depicted about the food insecurity and gender related issues due to the fact of climate change and also suggested to take strategies to adapt with climate change. Chowdhury et al. (2022), upheld the vulnerabilities cause of climate change in Bangladesh and said some necessary plans to adapt with climate change issue along with showing the barriers to adapt with that. Most of the papers showed the effect and impact of climate change in vulnerable states like Bangladesh and suggested plans to soothe this problem, but they didn't uphold the barrier to making consensus to solve this big problem. This research will identify barriers like politics and lacks of volition to save the world community. Climate change is one of the most challenging issues all over the world. Climate change is now a global threat to security.

Many nations are substantially afflicted by climate change, thus leads towards global instability. Climate change is directly involved with the economy because it affects the agriculture sector of a country, and climate change is responsible for fostering human risk and migration, which is the cause of the instability of a country. Bangladesh is a climate-vulnerable country, and this country is facing these bad effects from the invisible guest. So it creates a big security problem that is outside of the traditional security definition. Bangladesh's reaction to the battle against climate change is remarkable, despite the fact that it is a tiny, developing nation with a mostly agricultural economy. The role of international forums is remarkable for raising a voice to save the world community. As a climate-vulnerable country, Bangladesh's loss rate is high, but Bangladesh works perseveringly to adapt to climate change to save her country. As a developing country, Bangladesh needs support and assistance from developed countries, which are accused of being responsible for the changing pattern of the world climate. But because to climate-related bad politics, it has been seen that they are arbitrary in their support for nations who are susceptible to climate change. The severity of the situation as a result of climate change is growing. Bangladesh is the most sensitive nation in the world to the effects of climate change, and it now holds seventh place in the global list. Each year, climate change is responsible for the deaths of five million people. As a direct consequence of this, the nation's security infrastructure in Bangladesh is in jeopardy. The gradual shift in the global climate cannot be stopped in a single day, which is why many influential people have advocated for adapting to the effects of climate change. Despite this recommendation, it is important to note that developing nations do not have the resources necessary to develop a comprehensive strategy for adapting to climate change. This presents a challenge for nations like Bangladesh. The developed nations, who are mostly responsible for climate change, have a responsibility to assist the developing nations that have limited economies in order to assist the vulnerable countries in adapting to the effects of climate change.

Research Objective

- To identify the climate change impacts for Bangladesh because of hampering the security systems which take Bangladesh in vulnerable situation.
- To find out the major loses area which going to deter the development of Bangladesh.
- To illuminate the hindrance for adaptation policy to fight against this big global problem.

METHODOLOGY

This study will use descriptive analysis methods, including relevant information, article facts, etc. This research paper is mostly based on literary reviews such as articles, national and international magazines, daily newspapers, social media, books, websites, etc. This research will be completed on the basis of secondary sources of data.

Non -traditional security threat as climate change

Having a solid understanding of non-traditional forms of security (NTS) in the first place, being aware of conventional security risks such as Concerns about national security traditionally concentrate on threats to the geographical integrity and political sovereignty of the state, in addition to the state's fundamental principles and beliefs. Multiple interpretations of conventional security exist, examples that encompass the use of weapons, armament systems, and the armed forces. However, diplomatic strategies such as agreements, treaties, and alliances that aim to form specific relationships between governments for reasons of security are included in this definition. All of these techniques, along with the basics of traditional security, are continuously shifting as a consequence of developments in technology, new points of view, and shifts in the political climate. By the demise of the period known as the Cold War, non-traditional safety concerns including terrorist activity ruining the environment, changing the climate, trafficking in drugs, and trafficking in people, among others, destroyed customary defense conversation (Islam and Khatun, 2023). This led to a less contentious relationship between conflict, the military, and armament. Climate change is currently a worldwide problem and the source of natural catastrophes such as frequent cyclones, floods, heavy rains, and droughts. These natural disasters are disrupting global ecological patterns and creating insecurity in the global environment, food production, health difficulties, and migrations. Concerns relating to climate change qualify as a danger to this world's NTS. Since the beginning of the industrial period, there has been a steady increase in the emission of carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is the primary contributor to climate change and also contributes to the warming of the planet and the loss of the ozone layer. In 1940, the rate of CO₂ emissions was close to 5 billion metric tons, but in subsequent years, that number has increased to close to 38 billion metric tons. The states in the northern hemisphere that are known as developed countries as well as the newly industrialized countries such as China, Brazil, India, South Korea, Japan, Hong Kong, Taiwan, etc. are primarily responsible for carbon emissions, which is what caused the world to become hot and changed the nature of climate, which put the world in a dangerous position. In addition, the use of fossil fuels like coal, oil, and gas is one of the primary causes of climate change and is among the most significant contributors. Because of this, there is now a greater concentration of gases that contribute to global warming in the atmosphere.

Other activities, such as terracing for agricultural purposes, are contributing to the rise in the average temperature of our globe. The present emissions of greenhouse gases, along with the fact that humans are responsible for the growth in the greenhouse effect, have the potential to cause the planet to warm to levels that have never been seen before. This might lead to climate change, which in turn could have far-reaching repercussions on the environment, society, and economy on a global scale that no one could have predicted.

Multiple impacts in Bangladesh

Bangladesh is globally well known for the perspective of global climate change impacts issue because Bangladesh is one of the most climate vulnerable states in the world. According to the geo-strategic location of Bangladesh, she is a disaster-prone country in the world and every year natural disasters come to show their evil faces for several times. (Mallick, 2017). The new dimensions of severity of disasters are added which are for climate change. The frequent floods, draughts, cyclones, heavy rainfall, heat waves are now widespread and gradually the severity is becoming higher than the then.

Food production

Global food production has been significantly and widely impacted by changes of world climate. Shifting in ecosystems, rain patterns, worse weather occurrence, and temperature all have an influence. Increasing temperatures and changing weather patterns can alter normal growing seasons. This may have an impact on when crops are planted and harvested, perhaps resulting in lower agricultural yields. Crops and cattle may suffer damage from higher temperatures. Heat stress can impact animal health and production, diminish fruit and vegetable quality, and lower agricultural yields. Climate change has become a threat for agricultural sector of Bangladesh as Bangladesh is an agricultural country and most of her grains comes from the cultivable lands and according to Sikder et al. (2014), the economy of Bangladesh depends on agriculture. Crop cultivation may be impacted by climate fluctuation and change in both favourable and unfavourable ways depending on the region of the world. Increasing humidity, shifting weather patterns, and rising. The occurrence of climatic extremes impacts ecosystem and water quality availability, agricultural productivity, and subsequently large population food security (Hossain, 2019). 62% of Bangladesh's people work in the sector of agriculture farming to manage their sustenance from agricultural produce, making it the country's main economic sector. A whopping 87% of the population of the nation resides in rural regions and is either directly or indirectly dependent on agriculture (Islam and Khatun, 2023). Agriculture is crucial to the process of economic growth and greatly contributes to the GDP of the country. But climate change made risk in food production system as global warming responsible for climate change, which enhance the frequency of adverse weather that is actually evil things to the production of food.

Temperature and rainfall differences have already had an influence on crop productivity in a number of Bangladeshi regions. Due to the effects of climate change, Bangladesh's food production will be harshly impacted by a 4°C temperature increase, which will cause 28% decrease in rice production and 68% decrease in wheat production. According to estimates, in Bangladesh, the agriculture industry might experience annual losses of roughly USD 7.7 billion as the consequence of climate change. Within 20 years, the average annual rice output might decrease by 33% (Chowdhury, 2022).

Human risk

Climate change poses significant challenges to people's health and well-being on a global scale. These threats are the result of a wide range of direct and indirect repercussions that have arisen as a result of global warming, shifting weather patterns, and shifting ecosystem dynamics. The food we eat, the air we breathe, the water we drink, and the locations that shelter us are all subject to the influence of climate change. Alterations in the frequency or severity of severe weather events, as well as the development of particular pests and illnesses, may be two ways in which climate change may have an impact on the health and welfare of people. Increasingly severe and frequent droughts, storms, heat waves, rising sea levels, melting glaciers, and warmer waters may all inflict outright harm on animals, disrupt the surroundings they depend on for survival, and have a terrible influence on people's way of life. According to "Effects of Climate Change | Threats | WWF," risky weather events are occurring more often or are becoming more severe as climate change continues to deteriorate. It is particularly important to stress that people's health is in jeopardy as a consequence of climate change in Bangladesh, where climate-related ailments are already rather common. At-risk populations have a much higher incidence of diseases such as pneumonia, dengue fever, diarrhoea in children, and malaria. Recent rates of mortality from dengue, which reached 900 in 2023 (Dengue Hospitalisation on Rise Again in Bangladesh, n.d.), and frequent floods bring dangerous illnesses such as diarrhoea, malaria, and typhoid, which cost many lives every year in Bangladesh.

Human displacement

People are forced to leave their homes as a result of natural disasters such as floods, heat waves, droughts, and wildfires, as well as more long-term climate issues such as rising sea levels and worsening water stress (Prange, 2022). Bangladesh was one of the countries that was most in danger from the consequences of climate change, which included the increase in sea level, greater floods, river erosion, and more frequent and strong storms. These alterations to the natural environment may necessitate the relocation of a sizeable portion of Bangladesh's native population. According to one assessment, by the year 2050, around 15 million people in Bangladesh may be compelled to leave their homes, which may result in the largest exodus due to compulsion in the history of the human race. By the year 2022, the effects of climate change had caused the displacement of around 7.1 million people. River erosion in the Padma, Meghna, and Jamuna rivers, which engulf the houses of the bank area dwellers and the rising sea level of the Bay of Bengal in the southern part of Bangladesh cause salinity intrusion that affects the cultivable land, which is why people migrate themselves in the capital city as well as the major cities in Bangladesh, which makes the situation imbalanced. On occasion, they are involved in nefarious activities and the promotion of strife.

Response of Bangladesh for adaptation

Bangladesh is one of the country's most vulnerable to climate change. The success story of Bangladesh is the country's efforts to mitigate the effects of extreme weather. Bangladesh's exceptional economic success may be traced back to the decades-long commitment of government and private sector funds to making the country more resilient to climate change and prepared for natural disasters. Owing to the nation's proficient crisis prevention and environmental strategy, the overall death cost from storms has been lowered by a margin of 100 from 1970. However, the country is still at high danger due to climate change. Climate change poses a serious danger to Bangladesh's progress, particularly to the poor. Group of the World Bank, 2022). The inhabitants of coastal Bangladesh are among the most vulnerable to the effects of global warming. Although climate-related natural catastrophes cannot be stopped, their impacts may be mitigated via preparation and other measures. The government of Bangladesh has adopted a number of internal and international measures to address the issue of climate change. Bangladesh has been an outspoken supporter of global climate change initiatives. The country has joined other countries in signing the Paris Agreement and the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. The Climate susceptible Forum, an organisation of nations most susceptible to climate change, has also benefited from Bangladesh's leadership. Bangladesh has urged industrialised nations to implement the Paris Agreement's goals of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The government has also advocated for wealthy countries to provide funding to developing countries to help them adapt to climate change.

Domestic responses

To contend with the issues at hand that the region's changing climate has brought about, the government of Bangladesh has taken a number of actions. The nation has created a National Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan in an effort to lessen the effects of climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions, adjusting to the consequences of climate change, and strengthening the nation's ability to withstand severe weather. In recent years, Bangladesh has made considerable financial commitments to the development of energy that comes from natural streams such sunshine and blowing wind. In addition, millions of trees have been planted all throughout the country in an effort to curb the effects of climate change and forestall the erosion of coastal areas. The government of Bangladesh has also implemented a wide array of preparedness and response techniques in the event of natural catastrophes. The country has put in place a network of early warning systems as well as shelters in case of cyclones. In addition, the government has provided millions of individuals with education on how to respond to the situation.

Responses in international arena

Bangladesh has been a staunch supporter of ambitious climate action at the international level, where it advocates for the implementation of comprehensive climate action. This country has made it clear that it expects industrialized countries to reduce their releases of greenhouse gases and give

developing nations the financial and technical assistance they need in order to adapt to the effects of climate change. Bangladesh is one among the initial countries to ratify the Paris Agreement, setting a global target for limiting warming worldwide well under a two-degree Celsius rise over the period prior to industrialization. The goal of the agreement is to maintain a temperature increase that is well below 2 degrees Celsius. A document known as a Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to the Paris Agreement has also been submitted. This document outlines Bangladesh's intentions to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases and adapt to the effects of climate change. The position of Bangladesh in the international arena as a leader among nations that are susceptible to the effects of climate change The Vulnerable Twenty (V20) Group is a coalition of the 20 countries that are most susceptible to the effects of climate change (Khatun et al., 2022). Bangladesh is one of the countries that make up this group. In the context of the international climate change discussions, Bangladesh is also the head of the Least Developed Countries Group (LDCs Group). To combat the effects of climate change, Bangladesh is collaborating with the rest of the world community. In order to carry out its strategy to address climate change, the nation has secured financial and technical help from nations that are major contributors to pollution as well as from international organizations.

The action that Bangladesh is taking to combat climate change is admirable. It is a prominent voice in calling for bold climate action, and it serves as an example for other nations that are susceptible to the effects of climate change. The case of Bangladesh demonstrates that even the most susceptible nations are capable of undertaking significant actions to track the effects of climate change. In addition to the above, Bangladesh is also involved in a number of the international climate change initiatives. The greatest fund in existence for combating climate change is the Green Climate Fund. Bangladesh is one of the first liner recipients of funding, which has been used to support a variety of climate change projects, including renewable energy, energy efficiency and climate-resilient infrastructure.

The Global Environment Facility, or GEF, is a multilateral fund that gives financial help to solve issues with the environment worldwide to underdeveloped nations, including climate change. Bangladesh has already received a mentionable amount of GEF funding to assist its climate change initiatives. The role of Bangladesh in the global forum in terms of the climate change issue that helps to gain the Climate Technology Centre Network, or CTCN, is a network of experts who provide technical support to developing countries on climate change technologies and gain some important assistance like renewal energy processes, energy efficiency and climate resilient agriculture.

Challenges of Bangladesh to adapt with climate change

As shown in previous discussion, in terms of climate change, Bangladesh is among the most susceptible nations. Bangladesh is already feeling the effects of this threat. The government of Bangladesh has made progress in adaptation

but some hindrances are in action which made adverse to work properly to adapt with climate change. The challenges can be divided into two factors which are the internal factor and the external factor.

Domestic factors

The indication of domestic factor in climate change adaptation challenges can be addressed that the issues which are facing by The Government of Bangladesh to adapt with climate change threats. The domestic factor can be described as political factor as Bangladesh is ranked as having the 172nd lowest measure of political stability, at -1.15. This shows that political instability is most prevalent in Bangladesh which gives the ideas that Bangladesh is in instable situation politically and new dimension of threat climate change issue added and makes Bangladesh insecure (Rahman & Rashid, 2018). Political violence and riots are common incidents in domestic arena which outcast Bangladesh into unstable situation and rural communal violence is also in force (Moran, 2018). For the effect of climate change increases the contagious diseases which takes Bangladesh into risky position and aggravates political instability. The problem of political instability in Bangladesh deters the good governance to adapt with climate change.

Economic factor as Bangladesh is a small but densely populated emerging nation in Southern Asia and more than 160 million people lived there in 2013 and in Southern Asia, Bangladesh has the greatest population density (1,082/km²). Rural regions are home to around 77% of the population. The foundation of the economy is agriculture. As a result, 80% of the population lives in rural areas. Along with the poorest nation in Southern Asia is Bangladesh, which ranks as the tenth poorest nation in the world (Mohajan, 2013). Bangladesh is a developing country and gradually the economy of Bangladesh is in progress. Due to impact climate change on agriculture which hampers the food production target and ultimately it has a direct impact on the economy of Bangladesh. Bangladesh government already allocated money to adapt with climate change which creates pressure on the budget of Bangladesh.

Bangladesh suffers yearly losses from tropical cyclones of roughly \$1 billion. A devastating statistic given that the agricultural sector accounts for almost half of employment in the nation by 2050 is the potential loss of one-third of agricultural GDP as a result of climate variability and catastrophic occurrences like water shortages, and increasing sea levels, with a larger impact on women, 13.3 million people may become internal migrants during the next 30 years. GDP might decrease by as much as 9% in the event of catastrophic flooding. Increased heat, humidity, and health effects are expected to drive up the costs of environmental damage and natural catastrophes over time. In the longer term, Bangladesh will require at least \$12.5 billion, or around 3% of GDP, for climate action. Additional priority, carbon taxes, outside financing, and private investment can help fill the funding shortfall in part. Addressing the pressing issues of climate change and development will be essential (World Bank Group, 2022). This is a big challenge to adapt with climate change as developing and small resources country.

International factors

Political factors is that concerns about politics relating to climate change are a kind of politics that may be explored and resolved by consensus during climate talks. The fact that the globe breaks into two blocs based on the North-South division during climate discussions. The gap in concerns and points of view on climate change held by industrialised countries and developing nations is referred to as the "North-South divide" in conversations about climate change. Historically, industrialised nations, which are often referred to as the "Global North," have been responsible for the majority of greenhouse gas emissions. This is due to the fact that industrialised countries have access to greater resources, both financially and technically, to battle climate change. The countries of the Global South, often known as developing countries, are frequently more vulnerable to the consequences of climate change, while having less resources to adapt to or reduce its effects. The environmental saviour regimes like as the UNFCCC, the Paris Agreement, the Copenhagen Accords, and the Kyoto protocol were developed with the purpose of creating common ground in order to rescue the whole world from the adverse effects of climate change. However, it is important to note that both state and non-state actors are reluctant to observe the rules, norms, and values that they have established. For example, the 26th Conference of the Parties to the UNFCCC organised in Glasgow, Scotland, in November of 2021. Countries were seen as having a responsibility to make the most of the summit in order to establish an ambitious treaty to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases and to protect themselves from the damaging effects of climate change. In addition, there are certain geopolitical concerns that need to be addressed in order to reach an agreement about the mitigation of climate change for the whole globe. Therefore, these political variables provide difficulties for nations that are sensitive to climate change.

Economic factor denotes that from the industrial age the countries have been emitting CO₂ in the environment. This is still going on and the rate of carbon emission is not equal among states. The industrialised states are maximum from global north developed states and now the developing states like India, China, Brazil, Mexico along with newly developed countries like Japan, South Korea, Taiwan etc. are responsible for CO₂ emission which is the cause of global warming and ultimate consequence is the climate change. Thus, climate change and economic development are intertwined, and these nations do not wish to harm their economies. However, they can provide financial assistance to climate-vulnerable nations, as they did twelve years ago at a United Nations climate meeting in Copenhagen. By 2020, they have pledged to provide \$100 billion annually to less developed nations to contribute them by halting temperature rises and combating climate change. These are the challenges for adaptation with climate change faced by small size of economic country like Bangladesh.

CONCLUSION

A serious problem for Bangladesh is the non-traditional security danger of climate change. The nation is extremely susceptible to droughts, flooding, cyclones, and rising sea levels. The economy, society, and ecology of Bangladesh are already suffering from these effects. The government of Bangladesh is acting to solve the problems caused by climate change. A national approach and plan for action regarding tackling climate change that the government has created covers a range of adaptation and mitigation strategies. In spite of this, the government is having trouble putting this plan into action due to a lack of funding, a lack of technological know-how, and trade restrictions. Bangladesh can benefit from foreign assistance in coping with climate change. By offering financial support, technological transfer, and trade favors, this can be accomplished. The international community may also be able to assist Bangladesh in strengthening its ability to adapt to climate change. Although combating it is a difficult task, it is crucial for Bangladesh's security. Bangladesh can lessen its susceptibility to climate change and create a more resilient future by acting now. Taking action to counteract the consequences of climate change requirements can be a comprehensive adaptation method. Bangladesh needs to promote more effective climate diplomacy to engage all actors in negotiations to fight against climate change. Finally, everyone has to work together to lessen vulnerability and increase adaptive capability.

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